

Studying and understanding the oxidation state of DC04 CRS metal surfaces from an industrial standpoint, using IRRAS, XPS analysis: effect of preparation and surface treatments

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Abstract:

A comprehensive understanding of the surface chemistry and oxidation states of cold-rolled steel (CRS) DC04 grade is crucial for optimizing subsequent industrial processes, particularly preparation and surface treatments. Despite the widespread use of DC04 in industry, detailed studies on its surface chemistry after typical treatment remain limited.

This study provides a descriptive assessment of the surface oxide formed on CRS DC04 substrates under various controlled treatments, focusing on the surface preparation and mimetic surface treatments. Surface preparation and mimetic treatments replicate the acid-base environment experienced by CRS DC04 surfaces in industrial context. Indeed, cleaning protocols and subsequent treatments were systematically varied in terms of pH and immersion time. While X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is widely referenced in the literature, it is not routinely available in industrial settings. Therefore, this study centers in infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (IRRAS), a technique well-suited to the substrates and industrial constraints but scarcely reported for CRS DC04. By comparing IRRAS and XPS results, we demonstrate that IRRAS can reliably identify and monitor surface

oxides, offering a practical alternative for industrial applications. This work establishes a reference dataset for the surface state of CRS DC04, providing essential groundwork for optimizing future surfaces treatments processes.

XPS analysis revealed that alkaline cleaning (pH 10.5) produces a thin, mixed oxide/hydroxide layer dominated by Fe_2O_3 and FeOOH , with residual organic contaminants. IRRAS identified the presence and polymorphism of FeOOH (notably γ - and α - FeOOH), Fe_2O_3 , $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, and FeCO_3 , with their relative abundances strongly dependent on treatment parameters. Lower pH and longer treatment times increased oxide layer thickness and favored more oxidized species, but excessively thick layers may be fragile and less conducive to adhesion.

These findings highlight the critical roles of both oxide composition and layer morphology in determining surface reactivity and adhesion potential. This work provides a detailed analysis of CRS surface species as a function of treatment conditions, offering valuable insights for the rational design of surface preparation protocols to enhance adhesion performance in steel-based assemblies.

Keywords:

Cold-rolled steel surface, DC04, surface chemistry, oxidation states, IRRAS, XPS, IRRAS

Highlights:

- Descriptive characterization of the surface state of CRS DC04 under controlled, industrially relevant conditions.
- Relevance and effectiveness of IRRAS as a routine analytical tool for industrial applications involving CRS DC04.
- Identified Fe_2O_3 and FeOOH (α , γ) as main oxides.
- Showed pH and time control oxide thickness and composition.
- Provided a detailed protocol for tuning CRS DC04 surface chemistry.

1. Introduction

Steel remains one of the most widely used materials worldwide globally, particularly in the transportation industry, where its mechanical properties, durability, and affordability make it a preferred choice for the manufacturing of structures, bodywork, and critical components [1-2]. Its versatility also extends to other sectors such as construction, energy, and household appliances, further illustrating its central role in modern industrial development [3]. Among the various steel grades, cold-rolled steel (CRS) DC04 is of particular interest due to its specific properties and its widespread use in applications requiring subsequent surface treatment.

Despite the industrial importance of CRS DC04, there is a notable lack of detailed knowledge regarding its surface state and oxidation, especially under conditions that closely mimic real industrial environments [4]. While the literature is rich in studies [5-8], and good recent studies on general steel surfaces, specifically their resistance to oxidation and corrosion [9-13], there is a scarcity of data focused on the surface chemistry of CRS DC04 after typical industrial treatments.

One of the main challenges in characterizing the surface chemistry of steel substrates lies in the limitations of standard analytical techniques. Transmission techniques are unsuitable for metallic substrates, as grinding or dissolving the material alters the original surface state and thus give results that might differ from the original surface. Moreover, the low abundance of surface species requires highly sensitive analytical probes. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is widely recognized as the reference technique for surface analysis and is extensively documented in the literature. However, XPS is not routinely accessible in industrial settings due to its cost and operational constraints.

In contrast, infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (IRRAS) offers a practical and effective alternative for surface analysis, particularly for our systems and substrates. When compared to ATR (**Fig. S1**) IRRAS allows the detection of bands that are less visible or not visible in ATR. It is specifically true for organic bands. Also, for very small amounts of species on the surface, the ATR crystal (here diamond) gives a signal that can hinder the readability of the spectra. Despite its advantages, IRRAS remains underrepresented in the literature for CRS DC04, with only a few studies addressing its application to this specific steel grade. This lack of data motivates our work: rather than seeking to solve a specific problem, our aim is to provide a comprehensive, descriptive characterization of the surface state of CRS DC04 under controlled, industrially relevant conditions.

By systematically characterizing the surface oxides formed after various treatments using IRRAS, and validating our findings with XPS, we establish a valuable reference for the surface chemistry of CRS DC04. This foundational knowledge is essential for optimizing subsequent surface treatments and processes. Our work thus addresses a gap in the literature, demonstrating the relevance and effectiveness of IRRAS as a routine analytical tool for industrial applications involving CRS DC04.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The steel grade used is cold-rolled steel (CRS) DC04 from Rocholl. DC04 steel is composed of: 0.08 %wt of C; 0.40 %wt of Mn; 0.03 %wt of P; 0.03 %wt of S and Fe. The CRS DC04 is a mild steel which means steel with low carbon.

The geometry of the samples used is 100 mm long, 25 mm wide and 3 mm thick. This specific geometry was chosen to fit with IRRAS “chamber” and also to perform specific mechanical tests which follow a standard. A picture of the sample on the IRRAS chamber can be found in **Fig. S2**. For XPS analysis, the samples were carefully cut into 25 by 25 mm squares using suitable metal shears.

2.2 Surface preparation and mimetic surface treatment

Preparation and surface treatment of steels are difficult to manage due to the fragility and poor adhesion of iron oxides that form on the surface. In addition, the composition of the baths varies depending on the composition and structure of the steel used [15-16]. In this context the preparation and the surface treatment are crucial stages to control surface condition (morphology of the oxide layers formed) and, further downstream, adhesion properties.

2.2.1 Surface preparation - alkaline cleaning

The surface preparation prior to treatment removes any contaminants (grease, oxides, etc.) from the surface. After this critical step, the surface is chemically active enough to perform surface treatment, such as chemical conversion treatments [17]. Surface preparation also improves the adhesion quality of substrates, such as roughness, wettability and surface free energy [18]. Consequently, this step has a direct impact on the final adhesion properties.

The cleaning process consists of a pre-degreasing step to remove most of the dirt and oil. It consists of dipping the substrates in a heptane/isopropanol (50/50 in volume) bath for 15 minutes at room temperature.

The pre-degreasing is followed by an alkaline cleaning step to make the surface completely hydrophilic and suitable for treatment baths. The alkaline bath (pH 10.5) is prepared using Rhodoclean[®] EFC V2 surfactant, mixed with various potassium salts and sodium gluconate. Substrates are immersed for 3 minutes at 55°C. Finally, the substrates are rinsed with deionized water prior to the surface treatment step, or dried directly (in compressed air, then oven-dried for 5 minutes at 80°C) to obtain the “cleaned reference”.

2.2.2 Mimetic surface treatment

To study the impact of various parameters, such as treatment time and pH range, substrates were immersed in deionized water solutions with adjusted pH values. These mimetic treatments replicate the acid-base environment experienced by CRS DC04 surfaces, but do not involve any actual surface functionalization or conversion steps (such as the addition of polymers or hexafluoride).

Treatment times vary between 60 and 120 sec, while the pH values studied are 3.5, 4.5, 5.5, using H₂SO₄ or KOH for solution adjustment.

After immersion, the substrates were rinsed with deionized water, then rapidly dried with compressed air before being placed in an oven for 5 minutes at 80°C, to remove all traces of water.

2.3 Characterization

2.3.1 XPS

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were performed on cleaned reference samples to determine the elemental composition and oxide type present at the outermost surface of the CRS substrate. Surface analyses were conducted using a ThermoFisher Scientific K-ALPHA spectrometer equipped with a monochromatized Al K α source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) and a 200 μm X-ray spot size. During sample transfer, the chamber pressure was maintained at 10^{-7} Pa. Survey spectra (0–1100 eV) were acquired at a constant pass energy of 200 eV, while high-resolution spectra (C1s, O1s, Fe2p, and other relevant elements) were recorded at 40 eV. Charge neutralization was applied throughout the measurements. Depth profiling was performed using an Ar⁺ ion gun (500 eV beam energy), with a sputtering rate of 0.3 nm/s determined on a SiO₂ reference layer.

It should be emphasized that the sputtering rate for oxidized steel differs significantly from that of SiO₂. Specifically, for C-doped 52100 steel, the etching rate is only 0.23 times that of SiO₂. Consequently, oxide layer thicknesses measured by XPS and calibrated using a SiO₂ standard must be multiplied by 0.23 to obtain the true thickness on steel substrates. The depth profile was divided into 13 increments (0, 1.5, 3, 4.5, 6, 7.5, 9, 27, 45, 63,

99, 135, and 208 nm) to enable detailed analysis of the surface region. Quantification was based on Scofield sensitivity factors, and Fe2p and O1s spectra were fitted using the AVANTAGE software (ThermoFisher Scientific).

For the experiments the samples are wrapped with aluminum tape and attached to the sample holder.

2.3.2 IRRAS

The FTIR investigation of steel samples was carried out with a Bruker Tensor 27 using a quicklock Barnes Analytical Division, Spectra-Tech, Inc IRRAS (*Infrared Reflection Absorption Spectroscopy*) module which does not include a polarizer. The wave number ranges between 400 cm^{-1} and 4500 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The number of scans was 20. A plane Gold mirror general purpose grade (97%@750-FAR IR) was used as the reference. The baselines were automatically corrected using the "concave rubber band correction" method in the OPUS software with 10 iterations and exclusion of the CO_2 bands.

2.3.3 Single lap shear test

To assess adhesion performance and thus evaluate the impact of the formed oxide layer, both raw (as-received) samples and samples after cleaning were subjected to a standard industry test: the single lap shear test.

Samples are bonded together with a 25 mm by 12.5 mm overlap, and the bond line (adhesive film thickness) is $200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, controlled by the presence of glass beads (with a diameter between 150 and $250\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) within the adhesive itself. The adhesive is a commercial epoxy-dicyandiamide, Betamate 1496 F from Dupont company. The curing step is carried out in an oven at 180°C for 40 min.

The test is conducted by a Zwick Roell traction machine (model 30 kN ProLine) equipped with a 30 kN load sensor. The samples are placed such that the jaws grasp the sample tips over 50 mm. The pulling speed is set at 10 mm/min. The strength at break (MPa) which corresponds to the force required to break the adhesive joint. Five samples are tested per series (raw and cleaned samples) to obtain average values.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Impact of surface cleaning on the surface chemistry

Firstly, the impact of cleaning on the surface and/or oxidation state was studied. A raw sample and a cleaned reference were analyzed by IRRAS.

As seen in **Fig. 1** most of the spectra in this study will show: 1) An average signal-to-noise ratio that is still acceptable for interpretation, 2) The visible presence of atmospheric CO_2 and water vapor. These two facts are related to the very low amount of species on the surface. 3) A negative signal in the CH_x region due to a slight pollution of the reference mirror used. This pollution does not impact on the inorganic bands that are the main focus of this study.

Fig. 1 IRRAS spectra of raw CRS DC04 sample (a) and CRS sample after cleaning (b)

The raw sample has peaks at 2954, 2924 and 2853 cm^{-1} that are in line with C-H bending of CH_2 and CH_3 groups signaling the presence of an organic compound on the surface that could be close to a polyethylene structure [19-20] or a long chain alkane that which is consistent with oil, lubricants or grease [21] that can be applied to the metal surface to avoid corrosion [22]. The peaks at 1463 and 1376 cm^{-1} are attributed to C-H bending, while the peak at 726 cm^{-1} could correspond to C-H wagging.

Fig. 2 shows that the surface state of the steel sample before and after cleaning is different.

Fig. 2 Impact of cleaning on surface state of CRS DC04 sample

This is confirmed by the IRRAS spectra of the sample after cleaning: the cleaning was efficient to remove part of the organic molecules as evidenced by the disappearance of the CH_x vibrations but quite a few vibrations remain and identifying their nature is important for the surface chemistry of the clean sample.

3.2 Surface species identification

3.2.1 XPS results

As seen previously, the impact of the cleaning (surface preparation) plays a significant role in the formation of a new oxide layer. An XPS study by Wang & al [23], was used to characterize the surface chemistry of CRS after cleaning at different pHs. Alkaline cleaning was shown to better remove organic contaminants, resulting in a decrease in surface carbon and an increase in detected iron. In particular, at pH 9.5, the surface presents a fine, dense, FeOOH-rich oxide layer, favorable to the adsorption of a silane primer.

At acid pH (1.0), the oxide layer is thicker and more porous, while at very alkaline pH (12.4), partial dissolution of FeOOH is observed.

In our case, it was possible to observe various characteristic peaks on the high-resolution Fe2p and O1s spectra on the cleaned reference **Fig. 3**.

Firstly, the high-resolution Fe2p spectrum reveals several main peaks: 707.2 eV and 710.9 eV, corresponding to Fe⁰ and Fe³⁺ species (Fe₂O₃ and FeOOH), respectively [23]. The fitted Fe2p_{3/2} spectrum further confirms the presence of Fe₂O₃ at 710.7 eV and FeOOH at 713.7 eV, both characteristic of Fe(III) oxides. This therefore excludes the presence of Fe₃O₄. Additionally, two satellite peaks at 738.5 eV and 720.5 eV [23] are observed. These satellite peaks, particularly around 720 eV, are indicative of Fe³⁺ oxide states such as Fe₂O₃ and FeOOH, further ruling out Fe₃O₄ oxides [24].

These observations show that under current cleaning conditions (pH 10.5), iron oxide and hydroxide are formed and coexist. Nevertheless, the Fe₂O₃/FeOOH ratio of 4 shows the predominance of Fe₂O₃ oxide. According to the literature [25], iron hydroxides (FeOOH) are generally more favorable to adhesion than iron oxides (Fe₂O₃), due to their more reactive and hydrophilic surface. Indeed, OH functions favor the formation of hydrogen and/or covalent bonds. The oxide Fe₂O₃ offers a more inert surface [26], and therefore less conducive to direct adhesion, unless pre-treated or functionalized.

Fig. 3 XPS high-resolution spectra of a) Fe2p and b) O1s for CRS DC04 samples after cleaning

On the other hand, the presence of the Fe⁰ peak (707.2 eV) on **Fig. 4** indicates that the thickness of the oxide layer is around 2 nm thick, as metallic iron (the substrate) becomes detectable at the 6th depth level, corresponding to (7.5 x 0.23 ~ 2) nm of material removed. It is important to note that iron reduction artifacts under Ar⁺ sputtering are well documented. Papparazzo's work [27] specifically highlights that ion etching can distort XPS depth profiles, particularly by reducing Fe₂O₃ to FeO. Nevertheless, when XPS depth profiling is performed rigorously and with

careful consideration of these artifacts, it still provides reliable information on iron oxide systems, as demonstrated in our study.

This observation raises several points. Firstly, a very thin oxide layer tends to approximate the surface properties of the underlying metal. Consequently, such layers are often amorphous, discontinuous, or porous [26], offering limited protection against corrosion and insufficient insulation of the substrate [25-26].

Fig. 4 XPS Fe2p spectra showing the thickness of the oxide layer (from level 1 to level 13)

In terms of adhesion, it can offer reactive sites, especially if the layer is rich in hydroxyls groups (-OH), as discussed previously. However, if the layer is too thin or incomplete, adhesion can become inconsistent. On the other hand, a thin and amorphous layer tends to be less brittle, which can actually improve adhesion. Therefore, achieving optimal adhesion is a matter of finding the right balance or operating point between these factors. Finally, with regard to its stability, it will be more sensitive to abrasion or dissolution during subsequent treatments, which can be seen as an advantage, since the formation of a new, thinner and more controlled oxide layer will be more favorable to the application of downstream treatments.

Conversely, the high-resolution O1s spectrum (**Fig. 3**) reveals four distinct peaks. The first, at 533.3 eV, is attributed to C=O and C-O organic group, likely due to surface contamination. The peak at 532.2 eV is associated with physically adsorbed H₂O. The peak at 531.3 eV indicates the presence of hydroxides (FeOOH). Finally, the peak at 530.2 eV corresponds to oxygen in iron oxides (Fe₂O₃). Notably, the Fe₂O₃ peak at 530.2 eV is the most intense in the O1s spectrum, which correlates well with the Fe2p spectrum, the Fe₂O₃/FeOOH ratio, and the IRRAS analyses that will be discussed later.

This information indicates that the cleaning step has indeed modified the surface condition (oxidation), but that impurities still remain on the surface of the sample, and/or ingredient residues from the cleaning solution formulation, as seen in IRRAS.

In conclusion, this study confirms that surface preparation—particularly the cleaning pH—strongly influences the nature and structure of the oxide layer formed on steel. XPS analysis reveals the coexistence of Fe₂O₃ and FeOOH, as evidenced by the presence of satellite peaks that are characteristic of oxidized states, especially trivalent iron (Fe³⁺). It is important to note that binding energies may vary slightly depending on experimental conditions, which should be considered when interpreting the results. Additionally, the several O1s peaks are typically associated

with oxides, hydroxides or adsorbed water, further confirming the chemical modification of the surface after cleaning. While alkaline cleaning enables the formation of a thin oxide layer favorable for adhesion, the persistence of some organic contaminants highlights the need to further optimize cleaning protocols to ensure an ideal surface—both reactive and clean—for subsequent treatments. **Table 1** gives a summary of the various contributions that could be present on the surface of a steel sample and the nature of the bond and their associated XPS signatures [24, 28-32].

Table 1 Summary of the various XPS contributions possible for steel surfaces

Chemical species	Fe2p _{3/2} (eV)	Satellite (eV)	O1s (eV)	Bonding nature	Comments
Fe(0) Metal	706.5 - 707.0	-	-	-	Metallic iron, no Fe-O bond
Fe₃O₄ (Mixed Fe²⁺ / Fe³⁺)	709.5 - 710.8	~ 715 - 717 (weak)	~ 530.0	Fe-O (mixed oxide)	Magnetite, mixed valence
Fe₂O₃ (Fe³⁺)	710.5 - 711.5	~ 718 - 720 (strong)	530.0 - 530.3	Fe-O (oxide, Fe ³⁺)	Hematite, strong satellite
FeOOH (Fe³⁺)	710.5 - 711.5	~ 718 - 720 (strong)	531.2 - 532.0	Fe-OH (hydroxide, Fe ³⁺)	Goethite, lepidocrocite, etc.
Adsorbed H₂O	-	-	532.0 - 533.0	O-H (physically adsorbed water)	Surface water, not bonded to iron
Organic contamination	-	-	> 532.0 - 533.0	C-O, C=O	Adventitious organic groups

Thus, XPS gives a pretty good notion of what species can be expected on the surface of the clean sample, but it is not a technique that can be used on a daily basis in most labs. Nonetheless, this information is very helpful for the interpretation of the IRRAS spectrum of the cleaned reference.

3.2.2 IRRAS results

Based on the XPS results the presence of Fe₂O₃ and FeOOH is to be expected on the surface of these materials.

According to the literature, FeOOH powders can have multiple polymorphs: β-FeOOH (akageneite), α-FeOOH (goethite), γ-FeOOH (lepidocrocite) or δ-FeOOH (feroxyhyte) [33-34]. It is therefore likely that FeOOH on the surface of a metallic substrate may therefore also exist in multiple polymorphic forms. The sharp pic at 1018 cm⁻¹ on **Fig. 5** is very characteristic of γ-FeOOH (lepidocrocite) and here is likely paired with the 725 cm⁻¹ band for in plane and out of plan OH vibrations [35].

Fig. 5 IRRAS spectrum of CRS DC04 surface after cleaning

The peak at 481 cm^{-1} is consistent with the Fe-O bond since the peak is quite broad, it can be hard to differentiate between Fe-O related to Fe_2O_3 or a Fe_3O_4 . Thankfully, the absence of the 715-716 eV Fe_3O_4 satellite peak in XPS leads us to conclude that the 481 cm^{-1} contribution is related to Fe_2O_3 .

The peaks at 1463 and 878 cm^{-1} , according to literature [36] could be linked to an iron carbonate. Previous studies on corrosion of carbon steel pipelines also reported the possible formation of FeCO_3 on the surface of the metal [37].

It is also possible that these peaks are part of oil-like organic material that was on the sample and that could not be removed as observed in XPS, but the main CH_x peaks are absent which favors the hypothesis of carbonates (**Fig. 5**).

The question of the reproducibility of the surface state of the CRS after cleaning is presented in supplementary (**Fig S3**) with several cleaned samples. Aside from the carbonates, most species can be found on the surface of the four samples. It is then very likely that the carbonation is related to atmospheric carbonation during handling. Knowing that this species is a possibility on the surface of DC04 is interesting as it may either block certain sites for polymer adhesion latter or change the acid/base balance of the surface.

The (**Fig S3**) also shows that after cleaning the sample seems to retain its surface chemistry even after 15 days. The fact that the samples are from an industrial source means that the surface state of the raw samples can vary. It also means that the state post cleaning can also vary slightly (organic residues, carbonation etc.). This is why other treatments are also explored in order to find the most suitable one for the CRS DC04 samples.

A more acidic surface treatment (pH 3.5) was applied, and **Fig. 6** was obtained. Part of the organic contamination remained as evidenced by the peaks between 3000 and 2800 cm^{-1} but the contribution at 1464 cm^{-1} was removed.

Fig. 6 IRRAS spectrum of CRS DC04 surface after acidic treatment

Peaks at 1190 and 1058 cm^{-1} are visible and according to Q. Peng & al and Zhang & al [38-39], are related to the stretching vibration of the OH group of ferric hydroxide ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, FeOOH being a ferric oxyhydroxide) and could correlate with the large band around 3500 cm^{-1} [40, 33], even though in the literature the band is often referred to as either water [41-42] or OH bands without specific attribution [43-44]. In this study it is believed that the peak at 3550 cm^{-1} is related to a Fe-OH vibration for a few reasons: 1) the presence of the 1190 and 1058 cm^{-1} peaks, 2) on other systems, like oxidized silicon [45] or TiO_2 [46] the physisorbed water is reported at around 3200 cm^{-1} , 3) Moreover, in Fe doped zeolites, the Fe^{3+} -OH bands are known to vibrate around 3680 cm^{-1} [47].

Thus, in our case, the peak at 3505 cm^{-1} , in addition to those already discussed at 1190 and 1058 cm^{-1} , tends to characterize the Fe-OH bonds of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, which provides additional information compared to XPS regarding the determination of the nature of Fe(III) oxides.

Peaks at 1022 and 745 cm^{-1} again represent the OH groups of the γ - FeOOH while the 834 cm^{-1} is expected to be related to α - FeOOH . Lastly the Fe-O vibration of Fe_2O_3 is still below 500 cm^{-1} . This surface state is congruent with the results obtained in XPS.

This paragraph highlights the importance of the surface treatment parameters on the nature of the species that can be present on the surface of the CRS substrate. It should then be possible to fine tune this parameter by using pH and time as levers.

3.2.3 Single lap shear results

To further investigate the impact of surface chemistry on adhesion, single lap shear tests were performed on both raw and cleaned samples. As shown in Fig. 7, the cleaned samples exhibit a higher strength at break (35 MPa) compared to the raw samples (33 MPa). This improvement in mechanical performance demonstrates the benefit of the cleaning step.

The observed increase in adhesion strength can be directly correlated with changes in the nature of the oxides present on the steel surface, as previously characterized by XPS and IRRAS. Cleaning leads to the formation of a thinner, more reactive oxide layer, which provides additional hydroxyl groups and reactive sites for bonding. However, it is important to note that while cleaning enhances adhesion, the improvement remains modest. This suggests that further surface treatments, such as functionalization or conversion coatings, may be necessary to achieve optimal adhesion performance. Finally, these results highlight the critical role of surface preparation in modifying the oxide layer and, consequently, the adhesion properties of CRS steel substrates.

Fig. 7 Strength at break (MPa) of raw and cleaned samples

3.3 Impact of the mimetic surface treatment

After studying the surface condition (oxidation) of CRS substrates after alkaline surface preparation and given the fact that an acidic treatment led to a different surface state, it was then decided to study these same surfaces after wet mimetic surface treatments, varying treatment times (60 and 120 seconds) and solution pH (3.5, 4.5 and 5.5) in order to study the impact of these parameters on oxide formation and thus potentially predict the adhesion properties of these surfaces.

1) pH 3.5 - 60 sec and 120 sec

Firstly, the impact of treatment time (60 and 120 sec) at isopH (3.5) was studied using IRRAS, **Fig. 8**.

Fig. 8 IRRAS spectra of CRS DC04 samples treated at pH 3.5 for 60 and 120 sec

Based on the work done in the previous paragraph, it was possible to assign the various peaks.

For 60 sec treatment, it was possible to observe the broad Fe-O peak at 491 cm^{-1} , characterizing Fe_2O_3 oxides, and two other co-evolving peaks at 742 cm^{-1} and 1020 cm^{-1} , characterizing $\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$ oxyhydroxides. The insert shows the presence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ which is in line with the peak at 1122 cm^{-1} on the main Figure. There also seems to be a low amount of $\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$.

For longer treatment, 120 sec, most peaks observed on the surface are the same ones, minus the $\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$ that doesn't seem present, but the relative intensities are much higher. This indicates both an increase in the thickness and/or density of the oxide layers, particularly Fe_2O_3 , and the amorphous nature of this layer, since the peaks are relatively broad.

2) 60 sec - pH 3.5, 4.5, 5.5

Based on the Pourbaix diagram [23, 48] different species are expected with various pH. At low pH: Ferrous Fe^{2+} and Ferric Fe^{3+} ions dominate in solution but how will it translate once on the surface of a metallic sample? At mildly alkaline pH oxides and hydroxides forms of iron are expected and since those species are important for the surface chemistry, these are the pH that will be investigated.

Thus, the impact of pH (3.5, 4.5 and 5.5) on the nature of the oxides formed on the surface for a given treatment time of 60 sec was studied.

Fig. 9 IRRAS spectra of the impact of pH on the surface of CRS DC04

Fig. 9 shows that the pH has an impact not only on the intensity of the peaks but also their nature. As described previously, pH 3.5 shows peaks for γ -FeOOH, α -FeOOH, α -Fe₂O₃ and Fe(OH)₃. The sample at pH 4.5 still exhibits α -Fe₂O₃, α -FeOOH but likely also has some γ -Fe₂O₃. The amount of γ -FeOOH is quite low and there is almost no Fe(OH)₃. Lastly, for pH 5.5 the peaks are quite similar to pH 4.5 but with a lower intensity. Overall, the more acidic the pH, the more oxidated species on the surface.

3) Cross effects - pH 3.5, 4.5, 5.5 - 60 sec and 120 sec

Fig. 10 shows the interaction effects of time and pH on the surface chemistry of a steel sample. The pH 3.5 at 120 sec was too intense and was thus cut off but the full spectra is available in the supplementary (**Fig. S4**).

First of all, the lower the pH and the longer the treatment, the higher the oxidation-related peaks and the thicker and/or denser the oxide layers are.

At pH 3.5, the oxidation is strongly influenced by time, as the γ -FeOOH and α -Fe₂O₃ peaks become much more intense after 120 seconds. At pH 4.5, γ -FeOOH peaks are visible after 120 seconds, whereas they were not clearly formed after 60 seconds. This specific species needs harsher conditions to develop.

Fig. 10 IRRAS spectra of cross impact of pH and treatment time on the CRS DC04 surface

At pH 5.5, there is no significant difference between the two time intervals, suggesting that a solution at that pH is not sufficiently corrosive to damage the substrate.

This can also be seen visually on the various samples where the 120sec treatment shows a bigger “rust” effect than the 60sec treatment. (**Fig. 11**)

Fig. 11 Photos of the surface of the samples after various times and pH treatment

The pH effect is less easy to spot visually. Overall, treatment time and pH play a key role; they allow a fine-tuning of the surface chemistry to have species more or less favorable for future applications.

3.4 Summary

The species that were observed by XPS and IRRAS in this study are listed in **Table 2**. The species that were not observed but that are reported in the literature are also presented with *.

Table 2 Summary of the various species of iron and their signature in IRRAS and XPS experimental or literature

Iron bond	Iron form	Iron valence	IRRAS Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	XPS - Fe _{2p} ^{3/2} BE (eV)	Comments
Fe-O	Fe ₃ O ₄	Mixed Fe(II, III)	570 400* [33] 580 630 * [49]	709.5 - 710.8	Black or gray-black, metallic appearance
	γ-Fe ₂ O ₃	Fe(III)	~640 ~710	710.5 - 711.5	Bright red to red-brown
	α-Fe ₂ O ₃	Fe(III)	~490		
FeOOH <i>Hydrated product from Fe₂O₃</i>	α-FeOOH	Fe(III)	~ 680 ~ 840	710.5 - 711.5	Yellow-brown to brown
	γ-FeOOH		Coevolution: ~1020 ~745		Orange to red-brown
	β-FeOOH		847 696* [34]		Yellow to yellow-brown
	δ-FeOOH		1120 975* [34]		Yellow to pale yellow
Fe-OH	Fe(OH) ₂	Fe(II)	3727* [40] mostly unstable	710.5 - 711.5*	Green oxide
	Fe(OH) ₃	Fe(III)	~3500 -1190 -1058	711.0 - 712.0*	Brown oxide
CO₃	FeCO ₃	Fe(II)	1463 878	710.2* - 711.2 [36]	green-brown oxide
Pure Fe⁰	Fe metal	Fe(0)	/	706.5 - 707.0	-

4. Conclusions

Despite the widespread use of CRS DC04 substrates in various industrial applications, there is a notable lack of recent comprehensive information in the scientific literature regarding their surface state (particularly in FTIR characterization) and its influence on adhesion properties. This study addresses this gap by providing a comprehensive IRRAS-based characterization of the surface oxides on CRS DC04 after mimetic industrially relevant treatments, validated by XPS.

This study aimed at deepening the understanding of the surface state of CRS substrates to enhance their adhesion properties. Through comprehensive analyses—including XPS, IRRAS—we identified the primary surface oxides

present after alkaline cleaning and mimetic surface treatments. The main oxides detected were Fe_2O_3 , FeOOH (in it is α and γ polymorphs), and some FeCO_3 vibrations that might be specific to some samples. Some $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ are also possible.

Our results establish that IRRAS, a technique far more accessible for industrial environments than XPS, can effectively identify and monitor the main surface oxides—namely Fe_2O_3 , FeOOH (both α and γ polymorphs), and, in some cases, FeCO_3 and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. We demonstrate that treatment parameters, especially pH and immersion time, have a direct and significant impact on both the composition and thickness of the oxide layer. Notably, while lower pH and longer treatments increase oxide thickness, excessively thick layers may compromise adhesion performance [50] an insight of direct relevance for process optimization.

The innovative aspect of this work lies in establishing IRRAS as a practical, reliable tool for routine surface analysis of CRS DC04, a steel grade for which such data were previously scarce. By bridging the gap between laboratory reference techniques and industrially viable methods, we provide actionable knowledge for tailoring surface treatments.

In summary, our findings offer a new reference for the surface state of CRS DC04, supporting more informed and efficient process development for surface treatment and other adhesion-critical applications. This works thus contribute both scientifically and industrially, enabling better control of surface chemistry to meet the demanding requirements in a wide range of applications, including adhesive bonding, paint adhesion, and the adhesion of polymeric materials such as thermoplastics.

Fig. S1 comparison between IRRAS and ATR spectra for a Cleaned CRS sample

Made with OPUS 7.5 and Powerpoint.

Fig. S2 Picture of IRRAS module with a CRS sample

IRRAS allows the detection of bands that are less visible or not visible in ATR. It is specifically true for organic bands. Also, for very small amounts of species on the surface, the ATR crystal (here diamond) gives a signal that can hinder the readability of the spectra.

Fig. S3 IRRAS spectra of various cleaned reference and impact of 15 days aging for one reference

Made with OPUS 7.5 and Powerpoint.

Fig. S4 IRRAS spectra of cross impact of pH and treatment time on the CRS surface (full spectrum)

Made with OPUS 7.5 and Powerpoint.

Fig.S5 XPS high-resolution spectra background of Fe2p and O1s

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5. Bibliography

- [1] World Steel Association 2024 Steel statistical yearbooks (available at: <https://worldsteel.org/steel-topics/statistics/steel-statisticalyearbook/>)
- [2] H. K. D. H. Bhadeshia, R. W. Kerr Honeycombe, *Steels: microstructure and properties*, 4th edn. (Butterworth-Heinemann, 2017).
- [3] E. George Totten, *Steel heat treatment: metallurgy and technologies*, 2nd edn. (CRC Press, 2006).
- [4] P.L. Menezes, Kishore, M.R. Lovell, S.V. Kailas, *Tribology for Scientists and Engineers: From Basics to Advanced Concepts*, (Springer, 2011).
- [5] S H Chaki, Tasmira J Malek, M D Chaudhary, J P Tailor and M P Deshpande (2015) Magnetite Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles synthesis by wet chemical reduction and their characterization. *Adv. Nat. Sci.: Nanosci. Nanotechnol.* 6, 035009. DOI 10.1088/2043-6262/6/3/035009.
- [6] A. Mirzaei, K. Janghorban, B. Hashemi, S. R; Hosseini, M. Bonyani, S. G. Leonardi, A. Bonavita, G. Neri (2016) Synthesis and characterization of mesoporous α -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles and investigation of electrical properties of fabricated thick films. *Processing and Application of Ceramics* 10 [4], 209–217. DOI:10.2298/PAC1604209M.
- [7] M. Gotić, S. Popović, S. Musić (1994) Formation and characterization of δ -FeOOH. *Materials Letters* 21, 289-295. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-577X\(94\)90192-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-577X(94)90192-9).
- [8] M.Farahmandjou, F. Soflaee (2015) Synthesis and Characterization of α -Fe₂O₃ Nanoparticles by Simple Co-Precipitation Method. *Phys. Chem. Res.*, Vol. 3, No. 3, 191-196. DOI:10.22036/pcr.2015.9193.
- [9] Zhang, K., Shen, Z., Li, J., Ma, S., Gao, S., Wang, H., & Zeng, X. (2025). Anomalous oxidation behavior and enhanced corrosion resistance of a lean-Cr FeCrAl alloy in the oxygenated PWR primary water. *Corrosion Science*, 113452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2025.113452>
- [10] Zhou, Y., Hu, H., Peng, C., Liu, J., Zhao, Y., Shang, X., ... & Chen, K. (2025). A precipitation hardened austenitic stainless steel with excellent stress corrosion cracking resistance against high-temperature water. *Corrosion Science*, 113352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2025.113352>
- [11] Shen, Y., Shen, Z., Zhang, K., Zhao, Y., Dong, Z., Chen, K., ... & Zeng, X. (2025). Superior corrosion resistance and crack tolerance of FeCrAl coatings on Zr alloy under hydrogenated and oxygenated PWR primary water. *Corrosion Science*, 113492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2025.113492>
- [12] Zhou, Y., Chen, K., You, Y., Shang, X., Li, Y., Shi, H., ... & Zeng, X. (2025). Oxide stress and fracture susceptibility on a surface gradient microstructure of an additively manufactured steel. *Acta Materialia*, 121779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2025.121779>
- [13] Ma, Y., Jiao, Z., Huang, Z., Zhou, Q., Huang, T., Ran, X., ... & Wang, H. (2025). Exploration on the oxidation resistance of TiAlNbN films: Mechanisms of nanopore regulation and crack suppression. *Corrosion Science*, 113273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2025.113273>
- [14] Xia, Q., Hua, D., Shi, Y., Zhou, Q., Zhu, B., Yu, X., ... & Liu, W. (2025). Unveiling the dislocation mechanism induced by irradiation defects in austenitic FeCrNi alloy. *International Journal of Plasticity*, 104451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijplas.2025.104451>
- [15] J. Cognard, *Collage des métaux Applications, Techniques de l'ingénieur Systèmes aéronautiques et spatiaux*, (Editions T.I., 2003). <https://doi.org/10.51257/a-v1-bm7621>.
- [16] L.H. Lee, Molecular bonding mechanism for solid adhesion, *J. Adhes.* 37(1–3), 187–204 (1992).
- [17] M. Ruimi, *Traitements de surface des matériaux par voie humide – Dysfonctionnements: Origines, effets, solutions* (EDP Sciences, 2013).
- [18] A. Bechikh, *Traitement de surface et caractérisation de l'adhérence dans les assemblages métal-biocomposite*, PhD thesis, 2020. Available online: <http://www.theses.fr/2020CYUN1106/document>.

- [19] J.V. Gulmine, P.R. Janissek, H.M. Heise, L. Akcelrud (2002) Polyethylene characterization by FTIR. *Polymer Testing* 21, 557–563. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9418\(01\)00124-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9418(01)00124-6).
- [20] M. Bredács, C. Barretta, L.F. Castillon, A. Frank, G. Oreski, G. Pinter, S. Gergely (2021) Prediction of polyethylene density from FTIR and Raman spectroscopy using multivariate data analysis. *Polymer Test.* 104, 107406. DOI: 10.1016/j.polymertesting.2021.107406.
- [21] M. Sejkorová, M. Kučera, I. Hurtová, O. Voltr (2021) Application of FTIR-ATR Spectrometry in Conjunction with Multivariate Regression Methods for Viscosity Prediction of Worn-Out Motor Oils. *Appl. Sci.* 11, 3842. DOI: 10.3390/app11093842.
- [22] E. Galvan, A. K. Larios Galvez, A. M. Ramirez Arteaga, R. Lopez Sesenes, J. G. Gonzalez Rodriguez (2024) Electrochemical, gravimetric and surface studies of Phalaris canariensis oil extract as corrosion inhibitor for 316 L type stainless steel in H₂O-LiCl mixtures. *Sci. Rep.* 14, 23370. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-75423-z>.
- [23] Y. Wang, P. Puomi, W. J. Van Ooij (2007) Effect of substrate cleaning solution pH on the corrosion performance of silane-coated cold-rolled steel. *J. Adhes. Sci. Technol.* 21, 935. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156856107781393901>.
- [24] J.F. Moulder, W.F. Stickle, P.E. Sobol, K.D. Bomben, *Handbook of X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy: A Reference Book of Standard Spectra for Identification and Interpretation of XPS Data* (Perkin-Elmer Corp., Eden Prairie, 1992).
- [25] M. Stratmann (1987) The investigation of the corrosion properties of metals covered with thin oxide layers. *Corros. Sci.* 27, 869. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-938X\(87\)90043-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-938X(87)90043-6).
- [26] M. Stratmann, H. Streckel (1990) On the atmospheric corrosion of metals which are covered with thin electrolyte layers—I. Verification of the experimental technique. *Corros. Sci.* 30, 681. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-938X\(90\)90032-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-938X(90)90032-Z).
- [27] Paparazzo, E. (1986). XPS analysis of iron aluminum oxide systems. *Applied surface science*, 25(1-2), 1-12. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-4332\(86\)90021-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-4332(86)90021-8)
- [28] C. D. Wagner, W. M. Riggs, L. E. Davis, J. F. Moulder, G. E. Muilenberg, *Handbook of X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy* (Perkin-Elmer Co., Minnesota, 1979)
- [29] A.P. Grosvenor, B.A. Kobe, M.C. Biesinger, N.S. McIntyre (2004) Investigation of multiplet splitting of Fe2p XPS spectra and bonding in iron compounds, *Surf. Interface Anal.* 36(12), 1564–1574.
- [30] D. Briggs, J.T. Grant, *Surface Analysis by Auger and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy* (IM Publications, 2003).
- [31] R.M. Cornell, U. Schwertmann, *The Iron Oxides: Structure, Properties, Reactions, Occurrences and Uses* (John Wiley & Sons, 2003).
- [32] M. C. Biesinger, B. P. Payne, A. P. Grosvenor, L. W.M. Lau, A. R. Gerson, R. St.C. Smart, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 257, 2717 (2011) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2010.10.051>.
- [33] M. Veneranda, J. Aramendia, L. Bellot-Gurlet, P. Colomban, K. Castro, J. M Madariaga (2018) FTIR spectroscopic semi-quantification of iron phases: A new method to evaluate the protection ability index (PAI) of archaeological artefacts corrosion systems. *Corros. Sci.* 133, 68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2018.01.016>.
- [34] L. Mei, L. Liao, Zise Wang, C. Xu (2015) Interactions between Phosphoric/Tannic Acid and Different Forms of FeOOH. *Adv. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 2015, 250836. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/250836>.
- [35] G. M. Atenas, E. Mielczarski, J. A. Mielczarski (2005) Composition and structure of iron oxidation surface layers produced in weak acidic solutions. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 289, 157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2005.03.062>.
- [36] N. Chubar, V. Gerda, M. Szlachta, G. Yablokova (2021) Effect of Fe oxidation state (+2 versus +3) in precursor on the structure of Fe oxides/carbonates-based composites examined by XPS, FTIR and EXAFS. *Solid State Sci.* 121, 106752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solidstatesciences.2021.106752>.
- [37] D.P. Burkle, *Understanding the formation of protective FeCO₃ on to carbon steel pipelines during CO₂ corrosion*, PhD thesis, University of Leeds, 2017.
- [38] Q. Peng, W. Xu, W. Qi, C. Hu, H. Liu, J. Qu (2021) Removal of p-arsanilic acid and phenylarsonic acid from water by Fenton coagulation process: influence of substituted amino group. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 28, 63319. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-15157-x>.

- [39] G. S. Zhang, J. H. Qu, H. J. Liu, R. P. Liu, G. T. Li (2007) Removal Mechanism of As(III) by a Novel Fe–Mn Binary Oxide Adsorbent: Oxidation and Sorption. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 41, 4613. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es063010u>.
- [40] X. Wang and L. Andrews (2006) Infrared Spectra of M(OH)_{1,2,3} (M = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni) Molecules in Solid Argon and the Character of First Row Transition Metal Hydroxide Bonding. *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 110, 10035. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp0624698>.
- [41] H. D. Lutz, H. Möller, M. Schmidt (1994) Lattice vibration spectra. Part LXXXII. Brucite-type hydroxides M(OH)₂ (M = Ca, Mn, Co, Fe, Cd) - IR and Raman spectra, neutron diffraction of Fe(OH)₂. *J. Mol. Struct.* 328, 121. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-2860\(94\)08355-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-2860(94)08355-X).
- [42] S.A. Sallam, G.M. El-Subruiti, A.S. Eltaweil (2018) Facile Synthesis of Ag–γ-Fe₂O₃ Superior Nanocomposite for Catalytic Reduction of Nitroaromatic Compounds and Catalytic Degradation of Methyl Orange. *Catal. Lett.* 148, 3701. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10562-018-2569-z>.
- [43] P.K. Raul, R.R. Devi, I.M. Umlong, S. Banerjee, L. Singh, M. Purkait (2012) Removal of Fluoride from Water Using Iron Oxide-Hydroxide Nanoparticles. *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.* 12, 3922. <https://doi.org/10.1166/jnn.2012.5870>.
- [44] S. Sobhanardakani, A. Jafari, R. Zandipak, A. Meidanchi (2018) Removal of heavy metal (Hg(II) and Cr(VI)) ions from aqueous solutions using Fe₂O₃@SiO₂ thin films as a novel adsorbent. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 120, 348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2018.10.002>.
- [45] A. Poda, Interfacial engineering of microstructured materials, PhD thesis, Auburn University, 2010.
- [46] S. Hosseinpour, F. Tang, F. Wang, R.A. Livingstone, S.J. Schlegel, T. Ohto, M. Bonn, Y. Nagata (2017) Chemisorbed and Physisorbed Water at the TiO₂/Water Interface. E.H.G. Backus, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 8, 2195. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.7b00564>.
- [47] R. Kefirov, E. Ivanova, K. Hadjiivanov, S. Dzwigaj, M. Che (2008) FTIR Characterization of Fe³⁺–OH Groups in Fe–H–BEA Zeolite: Interaction with CO and NO. *Catal. Lett.* 125, 209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10562-008-9577-3>.
- [48] A. Kraš, I. Milošev (2024) Comparative electrochemical and thermodynamic study of cold-rolled steel, Al alloy AA5754, and Zn corrosion in fluoride and chloride solutions. *Electrochim. Acta* 502, 144819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2024.144819>.
- [49] L. Nalbandian, E. Patrikiadou, V. Zaspalis, A. Patrikidou, E. Hatzidaki, C.N. Papandreou (2016) Magnetic Nanoparticles in Medical Diagnostic Applications: Synthesis, Characterization and Proteins Conjugation. *Curr. Nanosci.* 12, 455. DOI: 10.2174/1573413712666151210230002.
- [50] J.J. Bikerman (1967) Causes of poor adhesion: weak boundary layers. *Ind. Eng. Chem.* 59, 40. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie51403a010>.